

REVIEW CERTIFICATE

Pak J Surg Med is delighted to Certify

Dr Muhammad Hamid Ch

for carrying out a thorough critical review of manuscript titled "DEGREE OF CAROTID AND FEMORAL ARTERY INTIMA MEDIA THICKNESS ON DOPPLER STUDY AND ITS CORRELATION WITH CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE (EARLY SCREENING) AND FUTURE PREDICTION OF CARDIOVASCULAR EVENTS"

Pak J Surg Med is thankful for a meticulous through peer review and it's our pleasure to have you on the peer review board.

Date of Review: July 24, 2020

Certificate Issued: August 03, 2020

Ammar Anwer

Chief Editor

Pak J Surg Med

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